

Survey on Typicality

Shared Representations of Culturally Typical Recipes

Damien Foinant, Maxime Michaud. 30 June 2026. Version 1.0

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Abbreviations and acronyms

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
AI	Artificial Intelligence	GA	Grant Agreement
CSI	Cognitive Saliency Index	PC	Project Coordinator
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ROLE	NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
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Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.5 (D3.5) presents the conceptual framework, methodology, and preliminary results of the *Sacrilege on a Plate (Soap)* study. This study derives from survey data on typicality conducted within WP3 (“INGREDIENTS – Data Collection”) of the RELISH project.

Led by Institut Lyfe Research Centre (LYFE) under the coordination of Fundació Alícia (FA), with the contribution of all consortium partners for the translation and cultural validation of the surveys, this work contributes to **Task 3.3** (T3.3) and supports the ontology and conceptual developments of WP4. Together with the data collected in T3.2, it contributes to building a contemporary cognitive map of European culinary heritage that will inform RELISH ontologies, recommendation systems, and participatory digital tools.

The deliverable reports the first phase of a three-step cross-cultural study conducted in seven European countries to identify culturally typical dishes, characterise the relative importance of ingredients within recipes, and establish an empirical framework for investigating ingredient substitution.

Beyond presenting the survey methodology and preliminary findings, the report introduces the concept of *structured flexibility*, which proposes that recipe adaptation should be understood as a continuum rather than as a choice between fixed tradition and unrestricted modification. This framework provides the foundation for the subsequent experimental phases of the project and contributes to the development of culturally informed approaches to sustainable recipe adaptation within RELISH.

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU's common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

Deliverable 3.5 (D3.5) was developed within **Work Package 3 (WP3)** and feeds into to **WP4**, with contributions from several RELISH consortium partners including the Fundació Alícia (FA), the University of Milan (UMIL), Institut LYFE (LYFE), City, University of London (CITY), the University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo (UNISG), and Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC). In particular, consortium partners contributed to the translation, cultural adaptation, and validation of the surveys across participating countries.

Within the RELISH architecture, WP3 provides empirical data needed to understand contemporary food practices and representations, while WP4 develops conceptual and operational frameworks for representing recipes, culinary practices, and food-related cultural knowledge within future digital infrastructures. D3.5 contributes directly to **Task 3.3 (T3.3)** and supports T4.2 by providing survey-based evidence on culinary typicality, ingredient centrality, and the perceived boundaries of acceptable ingredient substitution. Together with T3.2, this deliverable contributes to the construction of a contemporary cognitive map of European culinary heritage that can inform future RELISH ontologies, recommendation systems, and participatory digital tools.

D3.5 addresses a central challenge for RELISH: How can traditional recipes be adapted in response to sustainability needs, without assuming that culinary traditions are fixed or that recipes can be modified without cultural consequences?

The report does not argue that recipes are inherently rigid. Rather, it examines where flexibility may become constrained, for whom, and under what conditions. In this sense, the deliverable should be read as a data-oriented and exploratory framework for identifying potential “stress points” in recipe adaptation, especially when substitutions concern ingredients perceived as important for recognising a dish.

1.1 Description of the document

D3.5 presents the conceptual background, methodology, and preliminary findings of a survey on typicality, titled *Sacrilege on a Plate (SoaP)*. The study investigates how contemporary European residents represent culturally typical recipes and examines how these representations can be used to identify the perceived limits of acceptable ingredient substitution.

Rather than treating recipes as either fixed cultural artefacts or infinitely adaptable collections of ingredients, the study seeks to provide an empirical framework for understanding where flexibility may become constrained when recipes are modified. In doing so, the deliverable contributes data and concepts that will support the subsequent experimental phases of WP3 as well as the ontology and application developments undertaken in WP4.

The report is organised into five sections. Following the present introduction, it introduces the conceptual framework underpinning the study, describes the survey methodology, presents the preliminary findings from the first phase of data collection, and discusses their implications, limitations, recommendations, and future developments within RELISH.

1.2 Theoretical rationale

One of the major challenges facing sustainable food systems is how traditional recipes can evolve to meet environmental objectives while remaining meaningful to the communities that prepare, share, and recognise them. Many current sustainability strategies encourage replacing environmentally intensive ingredients with more sustainable alternatives, particularly through reducing the consumption of animal-based products and increasing the use of plant-based ingredients (Willett et al. 2019). Such changes inevitably involve modifying existing recipes.

However, previous work across food studies, anthropology, and cultural heritage research suggests that recipes should not be understood simply as technical combinations of ingredients. They are dynamic cultural objects that continuously evolve through social practice, migration, local adaptation, and historical change (Matta et al. 2020; Parasecoli 2022; Sigrist et Michaud 2023). Consequently, the challenge is not whether recipes can change—they clearly do—but rather **how these changes are perceived and under which conditions they remain culturally acceptable**.

Within RELISH, this question is particularly important because future recommendation systems and food ontologies will need to propose recipe

adaptations that are environmentally beneficial while remaining culturally meaningful. The purpose of the present study is therefore not to demonstrate that cultural factors influence food acceptance, which is already well established, but to provide an empirical framework for identifying **where the perceived boundaries of acceptable adaptation may lie**.

The study focuses specifically on **ingredient substitution**. This choice reflects both the objectives of RELISH and the methodological constraints of a controlled cross-cultural survey. Ingredient substitution represents one of the principal strategies currently proposed for improving the environmental sustainability of recipes, making it an appropriate entry point for investigating culturally acceptable adaptation. At the same time, recipes encompass many other dimensions, including preparation techniques, cooking equipment, gestures, ingredient origins, social contexts, and the knowledge of those preparing them. These dimensions undoubtedly contribute to recipe identity but fall beyond the scope of the present survey and constitute important directions for future research.

Importantly, the study does not treat authenticity or recipe identity as objective historical properties (see **D4.1**¹ and **D4.2**²). Throughout this report, these concepts refer to participants' perceptions of whether a modified dish continues to be recognised as a legitimate instance of the original recipe. Likewise, the study does not assume that recipes are inherently rigid. Instead, it investigates whether some modifications are perceived as more disruptive than others and whether these perceptions can be explained by the organisation of shared culinary representations.

The project implemented a three-step survey across seven European countries (France, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Ireland, Denmark, and the United Kingdom) to answer four research questions:

- Which dishes occupy the most salient positions within contemporary representations of national cuisines?
- Which ingredients are most strongly associated with these dishes?
- Can ingredient hierarchies provide an empirical basis for investigating the perceived limits of acceptable substitution?
- Which individual and sociocultural characteristics are associated with stronger convergence towards culturally shared culinary representations?

¹ D4.1 "Critical Framework for RELISH," on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/19922981>

² D4.2 "Operationalising Typicality and Sustainability," on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/21013174>

The broader contribution of D3.5 is therefore **methodological** and **conceptual**. It provides RELISH with an empirical framework for identifying where flexibility in recipes may become constrained in ingredient substitution. This work lays the foundations for the subsequent experimental phases of the project and introduces the notion of *structured flexibility*, which will be further developed and tested throughout the remainder of WP3 and integrated into the conceptual developments of WP4.

2 Conceptual Framework

This section outlines the development of the central conceptual contribution of this review: *structured flexibility*. It consults scholarly approaches to recipe dynamism and identity to consider the perceived limitations to flexibility or rigidity as a useful framework for studying recipe identity and ingredient substitution.

2.1 Recipes as dynamic cultural systems

Recipes are often presented as emblematic expressions of culinary heritage, yet research across anthropology, food studies, and philosophy consistently shows that they are neither fixed nor immutable objects. Recipes evolve through migration, technological innovation, environmental change, economic constraints, and everyday domestic practice, continuously adapting while preserving varying degrees of continuity with previous culinary traditions (Matta et al. 2020; Parasecoli 2022; Sigrist and Michaud 2023).

Anthropological research has long emphasised that food practices are simultaneously biological, social, and symbolic phenomena. Lévi-Strauss (1966) famously proposed that culinary transformations provide a way of understanding how societies organise relationships between nature and culture. Similarly, Douglas (1972, 1979) argued that meals possess a grammar: they are organised systems in which different components occupy different structural positions, contributing unequally to the coherence and recognisability of the whole. Rather than viewing meals as simple collections of foods, Douglas showed that their organisation reflects culturally shared rules governing classification, order, and social meaning.

Subsequent work has extended this perspective by showing that recipes function as cultural objects continuously negotiated through historical change, social practice, and collective memory (Turmo 2004; Calvo 1982; Matta et al. 2020). Recipes therefore cannot be understood simply as fixed lists of ingredients or instructions. They are

dynamic cultural constructions whose meanings emerge through repeated social use while remaining open to reinterpretation and adaptation.

This understanding is reflected in the conceptual framework developed within **D4.2**, which approaches recipes as evolving cultural entities rather than static heritage objects. Likewise, philosophical work on food ontology argues that recipe identity emerges from the relations among ingredients, preparation techniques, functions, and shared cultural conventions rather than from preserving an invariant composition (Borghini 2015; Borghini and Gandolini 2020). Consequently, sustainable adaptation should not be framed as a choice between preserving recipes unchanged or abandoning tradition altogether. Instead, it requires understanding how change is negotiated within culturally meaningful boundaries.

2.2 Shared representations of recipes

Although recipes evolve historically, they are also represented cognitively by the individuals and communities that prepare, consume, and transmit them.

Cognitive research suggests that recipes can be understood as **script-like representations**: organised knowledge structures integrating ingredients, preparation sequences, functional relations, and culturally learned expectations (Schank and Abelson 1977; Nguyen and Murphy 2003). These scripts allow individuals to recognise recipes despite natural variations occurring across households, regions, or historical periods.

Importantly, recognising a recipe does not imply that all of its components contribute equally to its identity. Rather, some elements may become more salient than others because they are repeatedly associated with the recipe through cultural experience.

The present study investigates one possible manifestation of these shared representations: **ingredient centrality**. Ingredient centrality refers to the relative importance that an ingredient appears to occupy within participants' shared representations of a recipe. It should not be interpreted as demonstrating that ingredients alone determine recipe identity. Recipes also involve preparation techniques, gestures, tools, places, ingredient provenance, and social contexts, all of which contribute to culinary meaning. Rather, ingredient centrality provides one empirically measurable dimension through which recipe representations can be investigated within the scope of the present survey.

2.3 From ingredient central to perceived substitution rigidity

Within RELISH, ingredient substitution represents a particularly relevant case because replacing environmentally intensive ingredients with more sustainable alternatives is one of the principal strategies currently proposed to support sustainable food systems Willett et al., “Food in the Anthropocene.” The present survey therefore investigates how participants represent ingredients before examining experimentally how substitutions are perceived.

Importantly, the study does not assume that ingredient substitution alone explains recipe identity. A recipe may remain recognisable or cease to be recognisable for many reasons, including changes in preparation techniques, cooking practices, serving contexts, symbolic meanings, or social conventions. Ingredient substitution is therefore examined as one dimension of recipe adaptation rather than as a complete explanation of recipe identity.

Similarly, the study does not seek to identify objectively indispensable ingredients. Instead, it investigates **perceived substitution rigidity**, defined here as the extent to which participants judge that a modified recipe no longer corresponds to what they recognise as an acceptable version of the original dish. Throughout this report, “authenticity” refers to **perceived authenticity**: participants’ judgments that a modified recipe remains a legitimate version of the original recipe rather than to any objective or historically fixed definition.

This perspective is consistent with ethnographic research showing that food substitutions are evaluated not solely according to nutritional or functional criteria but also according to broader systems of social meaning. Garth’s (2019) concept of *alimentary dignity*, for example, illustrates how people evaluate meals according to culturally shared expectations concerning what constitutes a proper meal. Likewise, studies of food authenticity have shown that perceptions of legitimacy emerge through social recognition and cultural practice rather than from intrinsic properties of ingredients themselves (Borghini and Gandolini 2020; Fibri and Frøst 2019).

2.4 Structured flexibility

The central conceptual contribution of this deliverable is the notion of **structured flexibility**.

structured flexibility: a framework applied to characterise the perceived boundaries of (un)acceptable modifications that affect the legitimacy or identity of a recipe.

Rather than conceptualising recipes as either rigid cultural artefacts or infinitely adaptable collections of ingredients, structured flexibility proposes that recipes are dynamic cultural systems whose adaptation is nevertheless not perceived as equally acceptable under all circumstances. Recipes evolve continuously, but some modifications appear more compatible with shared culinary representations than others.

Structured flexibility does not establish universal boundaries of acceptable change. It is a framework that can be methodologically applied to identify potential “stress points” where contemporary participants begin to perceive that modifications challenge the recognisability or legitimacy of a recipe. Neither are these stress points fixed; they represent empirical observations of contemporary shared representations that may themselves evolve over time.

Structured flexibility therefore differs from traditional notions of authenticity based on fixed canonical recipes. It recognises that culinary traditions are simultaneously stable and dynamic: they are stable enough to support shared recognition, yet dynamic enough to accommodate historical, social, and environmental change.

Rather than opposing heritage and innovation, the framework seeks to understand how adaptation can occur while maintaining cultural coherence.

2.5 Implications

The structured flexibility framework provides an empirical basis for operationalising culturally informed recipe adaptation.

The principal contribution of D3.5 is not to demonstrate that culture matters for sustainable food transitions, this is already well established across anthropology, food studies, and heritage research (Douglas 1979; Parasecoli 2022; Matta et al. 2020). Rather, it provides a methodology for identifying and operationalising **the perceived boundaries of acceptable adaptation** within contemporary culinary representations.

This contribution directly supports the objectives of **WP4**. By identifying culturally salient dishes, empirically describing ingredient hierarchies, and establishing a framework for investigating perceived substitution rigidity, the present work provides data that can inform recipe ontologies, recommendation systems, and participatory digital tools capable of integrating environmental objectives with culturally meaningful representations of European culinary heritage.

More broadly, the framework of structured flexibility may also support future dialogue with policymakers, cultural heritage organisations, and sustainability stakeholders. Rather than prescribing fixed notions of authenticity or assuming

unrestricted flexibility, it offers a way of understanding how sustainable food transitions can remain attentive to perceptions of recipe identities and the evolving cultural meanings attached to recipes, while recognising that these identities and meanings are themselves dynamic and historically situated.

3 Methodology

The *SoaP* study was designed to investigate how contemporary European residents represent culturally typical recipes and how these shared representations can inform the study of ingredient substitution. Rather than directly measuring whether recipes are “rigid” or “flexible,” the survey was designed to identify the points at which recipe modifications begin to challenge participants’ perceptions of a dish.

To achieve this objective, the project implemented a three-phase online survey across seven European countries (France, Italy, Spain, Portugal, Ireland, Denmark, and the United Kingdom). Data were collected through the Kantar online research platform using harmonised questionnaires translated and culturally validated by consortium members in each participating country.

The three phases were designed to progressively address the research questions on representations of a typical recipe and the study of ingredient substitution:

1. Participants identified dishes they considered typical of their national cuisine and listed the ingredients they associated with these dishes. This allowed the project to identify shared culinary representations.
2. A separate pretest identified ingredient substitutions that participants considered plausible for each recipe while remaining sufficiently distinct to challenge recipe recognition.
3. Participants evaluated modified recipes in which selected ingredients had been replaced. These evaluations were used to investigate whether substitutions affecting ingredients occupying different positions within shared recipe representations influenced perceived category membership, authenticity, confidence, and willingness to consume the modified dish.

Although recipes involve many dimensions, including preparation techniques, cooking equipment, ingredient provenance, social context, and culinary know-how, the present study focuses specifically on **ingredient substitution**. This choice reflects both the objectives of RELISH, where ingredient substitution constitutes a major sustainability strategy, and the practical advantages of manipulating ingredients in a

controlled cross-cultural online design. The present survey should therefore be understood as investigating one important dimension of recipe flexibility rather than recipe identity as a whole.

3.1 Participants

Participants were recruited through the Kantar online survey platform.

To ensure familiarity with the culinary traditions investigated, participants were required to:

- Be at least 18 years old;
- Hold the nationality of the country in which they completed the survey;
- Have lived in that country for at least the previous five years;
- Provide informed consent before participation.

The nationality criterion was used to maximise participants' familiarity with the culinary traditions investigated. It should not be interpreted as assuming culturally homogeneous national populations or excluding the possibility of multiple cultural identities. This was a pragmatic inclusion criterion intended to ensure that participants had substantial exposure to the culinary environment under investigation.

The first phase included 612 participants (307 women, 305 men, mean age = 48.2 ± 2.8 years), with 74–96 participants recruited in each country.

3.2 Research Phases

PHASE 1

Identifying culturally salient dishes and ingredient hierarchies

The first phase investigated contemporary shared representations of national cuisines.

Participants completed a **free-listing task**. They were first asked to write down up to six main-course dishes that they considered most typical of their national cuisine. For each listed dish, they subsequently identified up to five ingredients that they considered characteristic or important for preparing that recipe.

The study focused exclusively on main-course dishes. Desserts, beverages, snacks, and side dishes were excluded because restricting the analysis to a relatively homogeneous category of dishes also reduced variability associated with different culinary functions.

Responses were cleaned and harmonised within each country to merge synonymous terms, spelling variants, and culturally equivalent labels.

The **Cognitive Salience Index** (CSI; Sutrop 2001) was then calculated to identify dishes and ingredients that were both frequently mentioned and recalled early during the free-listing task. Within each recipe, CSI values additionally provided an empirical indicator of the relative prominence of different ingredients within participants' shared representations.

Importantly, CSI measures *cognitive salience*, not objective culinary importance. The resulting ingredient hierarchies therefore represent shared contemporary representations rather than historically fixed recipe definitions.

PHASE 2

Identifying culturally plausible substitutions

The second phase aimed to construct ingredient substitutions suitable for the experimental phase.

Participants evaluated several potential substitutes for selected ingredients from the most salient recipes identified during Phase 1. Rather than asking participants whether substitutions were acceptable, this pretest aimed to identify alternatives that remained both recognisable and sufficiently plausible to constitute meaningful experimental manipulations.

Whenever possible, substitutes preserved the general culinary role of the original ingredient (*e.g.*, protein source, vegetable, starch, seasoning) while remaining distinct enough to alter the recipe.

The highest-ranked substitute for each ingredient was retained for the experimental phase.

PHASE 3

Evaluating modified recipes

The third phase experimentally investigated participants' responses to ingredient substitutions.

Participants were presented with modified versions of culturally typical recipes in which ingredients occupying different levels of cognitive salience had been replaced.

For each modified recipe, participants indicated:

- Whether the modified dish still belonged to the same recipe category;
- How authentic they perceived it to be;
- How confident they felt about their judgment;
- Whether they would be willing to consume it.

3.3 Data processing and statistical analysis

Each phase of the study generated a different type of data and was therefore analysed using complementary analytical approaches.

For **Phase 1**, free-listing responses were first harmonised within each country by correcting spelling variations, merging synonymous terms, and standardising dish and ingredient names while preserving culturally meaningful distinctions. The resulting datasets were then analysed using the CSI, which combines the frequency with which an item is mentioned with its average position in participants' lists. An item receives a high CSI when it is mentioned by many participants and recalled early during the free-listing task. Consequently, CSI provides an indicator of the relative salience of dishes and ingredients within contemporary shared culinary representations.

CSI values were calculated separately for dishes and for ingredients. Within each country, the most salient dishes were identified and, for each dish, ingredient CSI values were used to establish a hierarchy of ingredient centrality. These hierarchies formed the basis for the substitution pretests conducted during Phase 2.

Participant-level analyses were subsequently performed to investigate whether convergence towards culturally salient dishes varied according to individual characteristics. To minimise the influence of idiosyncratic responses, a mean CSI

score was computed for each participant using only the ten most salient dishes identified within their country. This score was then entered into multiple linear regression models examining the contribution of demographic variables, culinary experience, familiarity with national and regional cuisine, identity-related measures, and socioeconomic indicators.

For **Phase 2**, substitution rankings were analysed using a reverse-ranking procedure. For each ingredient, the preferred substitute received three points, the second-ranked substitute received two points, and the third-ranked substitute received one point. Average ranking scores were then calculated across participants, and the substitute with the highest mean score was retained for the experimental phase. This procedure ensured that substitutions reflected collective culinary judgments rather than arbitrary researcher decisions.

For **Phase 3**, participants' evaluations of modified recipes were collected on continuous rating scales measuring perceived category membership, perceived authenticity, confidence, and willingness to consume the modified dish. These data will be analysed using mixed-effects modelling to examine whether substitutions targeting ingredients occupying different levels of cognitive salience produce different responses while accounting for both participant-level and recipe-level variability. These analyses will be presented in later publications and D4.7 following completion of data collection.

Throughout the analyses, the emphasis is placed on identifying shared patterns of culinary representation rather than establishing objective definitions of recipe identity. The statistical procedures are therefore intended to characterise contemporary collective representations of typical recipes and to provide an empirical basis for investigating how these representations may influence perceptions of ingredient substitution.

3.4 Ethical considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards governing research involving human participants. Participation was voluntary and based on informed consent obtained electronically before the beginning of the survey. Participants were informed of the purpose of the research, the anonymous treatment of their responses, and their right to withdraw at any stage prior to submission of the questionnaire.

No personally identifying information was retained within the analytical dataset. All data were pseudonymised before analysis and stored securely in accordance with the

RELISH Data Management Plan (DMP) and applicable European data protection regulations (GDPR).

The survey protocol was harmonised across the seven participating countries. Questionnaires were translated and culturally adapted by consortium partners to ensure conceptual equivalence while preserving country-specific culinary terminology. This collaborative validation process was essential to maximise the comparability of the data while respecting the cultural specificities of each national culinary context.

4 Results

At the time of writing, the study has completed the first phase of data collection and analysis, corresponding to the identification of culturally salient dishes and ingredient representations across seven European countries.

These preliminary analyses addressed three objectives, which are to:

1. Identify culturally salient dishes within each national context;
2. Characterise the relative salience of ingredients within these dishes;
3. Examine individual differences associated with convergence towards culturally shared culinary representations.

Taken together, the findings provide an empirical description of contemporary shared culinary representations across the participating countries. Rather than testing substitution acceptability directly, this first phase establishes the empirical basis on which the subsequent experimental phases will investigate how ingredient substitutions are perceived.

4.1 Culturally salient dishes across countries

4.1.1 *National convergence in culinary representations*

The first stage of the analyses aimed to identify the dishes most strongly associated with each national cuisine.

Cultural salience was operationalised using the CSI, which combines the frequency with which an item is mentioned with its average position in participants' free-

listing responses. Consequently, dishes with high CSI values are both widely shared and readily recalled within participants' representations of their national cuisine.

Across all seven countries, participants showed substantial convergence towards a relatively limited repertoire of emblematic dishes. This finding indicates that participants shared common reference points when describing their national cuisine, although the degree of convergence varied across countries.

4.1.2 Cross-cultural patterns

The dishes most frequently identified differed according to national culinary contexts (Figure 1).

Italian participants converged strongly around dishes such as *pizza*, *carbonara*, *lasagna*, and *pasta al ragù*. Spanish participants most frequently identified *paella*, *tortilla de patatas*, and *cocido*, whereas Portuguese participants consistently associated national cuisine with cod-based dishes and slow-cooked meat preparations.

French participants most frequently listed regionally rooted dishes such as *bœuf bourguignon*, *cassoulet*, *blanquette de veau*, and *tartiflette*. Participants from Ireland, the United Kingdom, and Denmark frequently identified dishes including *shepherd's pie*, *fish and chips*, *Irish stew*, *frikadeller*, and *stegt flæsk*.

These observations illustrate that participants from each country converged around recognisable sets of representative dishes while also reflecting differences in the composition of national culinary repertoires. The present analyses describe these shared representations but do not aim to establish definitive or exhaustive descriptions of national cuisines.

Overall, the free-listing task revealed substantial agreement among participants regarding dishes considered representative of their national cuisine. These findings suggest that contemporary culinary representations contain identifiable common reference points that can be used as the basis for subsequent project phases.

Figure 1: Top 6 of the most typical recipes across the seven European countries.

4.2 Ingredient salience within recipes

4.2.1 Relative salience of ingredients

For each selected dish, CSI values were also calculated for the ingredients listed by participants.

This analysis allowed ingredients to be ranked according to their relative salience within participants' shared representations of each recipe.

Across countries and recipes, participants consistently attributed different levels of salience to ingredients. Within a given recipe, some ingredients were mentioned both more frequently and earlier than others, whereas additional ingredients appeared less consistently across participants.

These results indicate that ingredient salience is not uniformly distributed within participants' recipe representations.

4.2.2 Illustrative examples

Several recipes illustrated this pattern particularly clearly (Figure 2).

For example, rice consistently occupied the highest salience positions within representations of *paella*, beef within *bœuf bourguignon*, cod within Portuguese cod dishes, and pork within several Danish recipes.

In contrast, aromatic vegetables, sauces, seasonings, garnishes, and accompaniment ingredients generally occupied lower salience positions.

Importantly, these hierarchies emerged entirely from participant-generated responses rather than expert classifications or predefined recipe descriptions.

The present analyses show that participants consistently differentiated ingredients according to their salience within recipes.

However, ingredient salience should not be interpreted as demonstrating that certain ingredients are objectively indispensable or that they alone determine recipe identity. Ingredients may occupy prominent positions because they are strongly associated with the name, symbolic meaning, culinary function, or cultural image of a dish. The subsequent experimental phases will therefore examine whether ingredients occupying different levels of salience also differ in their influence on participants' evaluations of modified recipes.

Figure 2: Examples of typical recipes' centrality of ingredients.

4.3 Predictors of convergence toward culturally salient dishes

4.3.1 Objectives

The study additionally explored whether convergence towards culturally salient dishes varied according to demographic, sociocultural, and experiential variables.

Participant-level salience scores were calculated by summing the CSI values of the ten most salient dishes identified within each national dataset. Higher scores therefore reflected stronger convergence towards the dishes most commonly shared within participants' national culinary representations.

Predictors included age, gender, culinary experience, years lived in the country, familiarity with national cuisine, familiarity with regional cuisine, consumption frequency, identity-related measures, education, occupation, and subjective financial situation.

4.3.2 Results

The final regression model was statistically significant ($F(3, 503) = 4.25, p = .006, R^2 = .025$), although it explained a relatively modest proportion of the observed variance.

Three variables were significantly associated with participant-level salience scores.

Greater familiarity with national cuisine was positively associated with convergence towards highly salient dishes ($\beta = 0.120, t(503) = 2.33, p = .020$). Conversely, greater familiarity with regional cuisine was negatively associated with participant-level salience scores ($\beta = -0.135, t(503) = -2.62, p = .009$). Subjective financial situation also showed a positive association with convergence towards highly salient dishes ($\beta = 0.097, t(503) = 2.19, p = .029$).

These associations should be interpreted cautiously given the modest proportion of explained variance. They nevertheless suggest that familiarity with different levels of culinary culture and subjective socioeconomic position may contribute to variation in how participants represent their national cuisine.

4.4 Summary of preliminary interpretations

The first phase of the project provides an empirical description of contemporary shared culinary representations across seven European countries.

Three main observations emerge from the analyses:

1. Participants consistently converged around relatively stable repertoires of culturally salient dishes within each national context.
2. Ingredients differed systematically in their relative salience within these shared recipe representations, indicating that participants did not represent recipes as undifferentiated collections of ingredients.
3. Convergence towards culturally salient dishes was associated with familiarity with national cuisine, familiarity with regional cuisine, and subjective financial situation, although these relationships remained modest.

These findings should not be interpreted as demonstrating that recipes possess objectively fixed structures or that ingredient salience alone determines recipe identity. Rather, they identify shared patterns in contemporary culinary representations that provide an empirical basis for investigating perceptions of ingredient substitution.

The subsequent phases of the project will examine whether substitutions targeting ingredients occupying different positions within these shared representations differentially influence perceived category membership, perceived authenticity, confidence, and willingness to consume modified recipes.

5 Discussion

The first phase of the *SoaP* study provides an empirical description of how participants across seven European countries represent culturally typical recipes. Rather than seeking to define authentic recipes or identify historically correct versions of traditional dishes, the study documents contemporary shared culinary representations and explores how these representations can inform the study of recipe adaptation. In doing so, it provides the empirical foundation for the subsequent experimental phases of **WP3** and contributes to the conceptual developments undertaken in **WP4**.

5.1 Shared representations

The analyses show that participants consistently converged around relatively small repertoires of culturally salient dishes and that, within these shared representations, ingredients differed systematically in their cognitive salience. Importantly, these findings concern *shared representations* rather than objective properties of recipes. They do not imply that recipes possess fixed or immutable structures, nor that ingredients alone determine recipe identity. They indicate that participants do not represent recipes as undifferentiated collections of ingredients, suggesting that some components are more strongly associated than others with the contemporary recognition of particular dishes.

This distinction is important because it reconciles the present findings with broader anthropological and philosophical perspectives on food. Numerous authors have argued that recipes are dynamic cultural objects that continually evolve through migration, technological innovation, environmental change, and everyday domestic practice (Douglas 1979; Calvo 1982; Turmo 2004; Matta et al. 2020; Parasecoli 2022). Likewise, Borghini (2015) argues that recipe identity does not depend on preserving

an invariant list of ingredients and instead emerges from a broader network of culinary practices, functions, and shared conventions.

5.1.1 Organisation of flexibility

The present results should not be interpreted as evidence against recipe flexibility. They suggest that **flexibility itself may be organised**: although recipes evolve, not every modification is necessarily perceived as equally compatible with contemporary shared representations.

This observation forms the basis of the concept of **structured flexibility** proposed in this deliverable. It is well established across anthropology, food studies, sustainability research, and philosophy that cultural factors influence food transitions and representations. The structural flexibility framework is useful for identifying where the perceived “stress points” of recipe adaptation may emerge. In other words, the study shifts the question from *whether* recipes change to **how changes are perceived** and **which modifications** are more likely to challenge the recognisability of a recipe for particular groups of people.

5.1.2 Context and cultural belonging

Furthermore, the “stress points” that emerge should likewise not be understood as fixed cultural boundaries. Culinary representations are themselves dynamic and continuously renegotiated. What appears unacceptable today may become ordinary tomorrow as dietary practices, technologies, environmental constraints, and cultural norms evolve. Conversely, some features may remain remarkably stable because they continue to function as powerful symbolic markers of culinary identity. The framework proposed here therefore does not seek to define permanent rules of authenticity, but rather to provide an empirical method for examining how shared expectations are organised at a **particular moment in time**.

The analyses of individual differences further support this interpretation. Participants who reported greater familiarity with their national cuisine showed stronger convergence towards nationally salient dishes, whereas greater familiarity with regional cuisine was associated with more diverse representations.

Although these associations were modest, they suggest that culinary representations operate simultaneously at **multiple levels of cultural belonging**. Rather than opposing national and regional cuisines, the findings indicate that different forms of culinary experience may orient attention towards different parts of the culinary repertoire. Similarly, the association between subjective financial comfort and convergence towards highly salient dishes raises interesting questions regarding the

relationship between culinary representations, cultural participation, and gastronomic capital. While the present analyses cannot establish the mechanisms underlying these associations, they suggest fruitful directions for future interdisciplinary research integrating sociology, anthropology, and food studies.

5.2 Ingredient substitution focus

The present work illustrates both the **potential** and the **limits** of focusing on ingredient substitution. Ingredient substitution was selected because it represents one of the principal strategies currently proposed for improving the environmental sustainability of recipes (Willett et al. 2019) and because it can be manipulated experimentally in a controlled manner across cultures. The study acknowledges that recipes are constituted by far more than ingredients alone. Preparation techniques, cooking equipment, gestures, ingredient provenance, meal structure, social occasions, religious prescriptions, and family traditions all contribute to how recipes are recognised and transmitted. The present study should therefore be understood as investigating **one empirically tractable dimension** of recipe flexibility rather than providing a complete account of recipe identity.

5.3 Applications

Within RELISH, these findings provide a direct contribution to the development of culturally informed digital tools. By identifying culturally salient dishes and describing the relative salience of ingredients within contemporary recipe representations, D3.5 establishes an empirical basis for selecting substitutions that can subsequently be evaluated experimentally. More broadly, the concept of *structured flexibility* offers a framework that may support further development in recipe ontologies, recommendation systems, and participatory applications capable of integrating sustainability objectives with culturally meaningful representations of European culinary heritage.

Rather than treating recipes as either immutable heritage objects or infinitely adaptable ingredient lists, such tools may instead represent recipe adaptation as a continuum in which modifications differ in their perceived cultural consequences.

5.4 Multi-disciplinarity

Finally, the present findings highlight the value of combining cognitive psychology with anthropology, philosophy, food studies, and sociology in the study of sustainable food transitions. Cognitive approaches provide methods for investigating shared

representations, while anthropological and philosophical perspectives situate these representations within broader historical, symbolic, and social processes.

Bringing these perspectives together allows RELISH to consider contemporary culinary representations and documentation practices with a richer understanding of how European recipes can evolve while maintaining their cultural significance. Thus, the principal contribution of D3.5 lies less in identifying fixed limits to recipe adaptation than in providing a methodology for investigating how those limits are perceived, negotiated, and transformed over time.

6 Limitations

The present deliverable reports the first phase of the *SoaP* study and should therefore be interpreted within the scope of its methodological choices.

A first limitation concerns the exclusive focus on **ingredient substitution**. This choice was deliberate and reflects both the objectives of RELISH and the practical constraints of a controlled cross-cultural online survey. Ingredient substitution represents one of the principal strategies currently proposed for **improving the environmental sustainability** of recipes and therefore provides an appropriate starting point for investigating culturally acceptable adaptation. Nevertheless, recipes are not defined solely by their ingredients. Their identity also emerges from preparation techniques, cooking equipment, ingredient provenance, serving practices, social occasions, sensory qualities, and the knowledge and skills of those preparing them. These dimensions were intentionally held constant in the present study and remain important avenues for future investigation.

Closely related to this point, the survey should not be interpreted as identifying objectively indispensable ingredients or definitive recipe compositions. The CSI captures shared **contemporary** representations rather than historical authenticity or culinary correctness. Ingredients occupying high levels of salience may do so because of their culinary function, their symbolic association with the dish, their presence in the recipe's name, or their role in broader cultural narratives. The present survey cannot disentangle these different sources of salience, and the subsequent experimental phases will be necessary to determine whether salience predicts participants' evaluations of ingredient substitutions.

A second limitation concerns the use of **hypothetical judgments**. Participants evaluated imagined modifications to recipes rather than preparing or consuming the modified dishes themselves. Consequently, the present findings describe perceptions of recipe adaptation rather than actual food choices or eating behaviour. Future

studies combining experimental tasting, behavioural observations, or real-world cooking situations would provide an important extension of the present work by examining whether perceived acceptability translates into actual consumption decisions.

A third limitation relates to **the populations investigated**. The study focused on participants holding the nationality of—and residing within—the country whose cuisine they evaluated in order to maximise familiarity with the culinary traditions under investigation. This pragmatic design choice inevitably simplifies the complexity of contemporary European societies, where culinary identities are often shaped by migration, multicultural households, religious traditions, and transnational food practices. Future research should therefore examine how multiple cultural affiliations, diasporic communities, and culturally diverse populations negotiate recipe adaptation.

Finally, the present analyses provide a **cross-sectional description** of contemporary culinary representations. They do not imply that these representations are fixed over time. Culinary traditions continually evolve through environmental change, technological innovation, migration, changing dietary practices, and broader social transformations (Matta et al. 2020; Parasecoli 2022; Sigrist and Michaud 2023). The boundaries of acceptable adaptation identified in this study should therefore be understood as reflecting contemporary shared representations rather than permanent characteristics of European cuisines.

7 Future Phases

The subsequent phases of the *SoaP* study will build directly upon the empirical framework established in the present deliverable.

The next stage will experimentally investigate whether ingredient substitutions targeting different levels of cognitive salience influence participants' perceptions of category membership, perceived authenticity, confidence, and willingness to consume modified recipes. These experiments will provide the first direct test of whether the ingredient hierarchies identified during Phase 1 can predict judgments of recipe adaptation.

Beyond testing ingredient substitution, the framework developed here opens several new directions for future research. One priority would be to investigate additional components contributing to recipe identity, including preparation techniques, cooking equipment, ingredient origin, serving practices, and the social context in which dishes are prepared and consumed. Such work provides a more comprehensive

understanding of how multiple dimensions of recipes jointly contribute to perceptions of recognisability and acceptable adaptation.

Future studies should also examine how recipe flexibility varies across different forms of cultural belonging. In addition to national and regional culinary traditions, perceptions of recipe identity may be shaped by religious food practices, vegetarian and vegan lifestyles, health-related dietary restrictions, family traditions, and multicultural or transnational food experiences. Exploring these dimensions would extend the present framework beyond national cuisines and better reflect the diversity of contemporary European food practices.

Another promising direction concerns the **temporal dynamics** of culinary representations. The present findings provide a snapshot of contemporary perceptions, but the concept of structured flexibility also implies that these perceptions may evolve. Repeating similar surveys over time would make it possible to examine how sustainability transitions, migration, changing consumption habits, technological innovation, or broader cultural transformations reshape the perceived boundaries of acceptable recipe adaptation. Such longitudinal work would provide valuable evidence on how culinary heritage evolves while maintaining continuity with shared cultural traditions.

Within RELISH, the empirical framework developed in D3.5 will support the ontology and application developments undertaken in WP4 by providing data on culturally salient dishes, ingredient representations, and potential stress points in recipe adaptation. Rather than prescribing fixed notions of authenticity, these data can help future recommendation systems identify modifications that are more likely to be perceived as culturally coherent while remaining compatible with sustainability objectives.

More broadly, the concept of *structured flexibility* offers opportunities beyond the immediate scope of the project. It provides a framework that could support dialogue with policymakers, cultural heritage institutions, educational organisations, and sustainability stakeholders seeking to encourage food transitions without reducing culinary heritage to either static traditions or unrestricted innovation. By recognising that recipes evolve while remaining embedded within shared cultural representations, the framework may contribute to more culturally informed approaches to sustainable food policy and digital food innovation.

8 Conclusion

From representations to practice, recipes can be highly flexible and rigidly stabilised across time and space. When considering recipes as forms of culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH), these considerations—among others reported in previous RELISH outputs—present challenges to navigating how typicality and recipe identity are salient elements of culinary heritage and gastronomic practice. Additionally, integrating sustainability measures can risk inadvertently undermining or ignoring how perceptions of recipe identity may impact the success of environmental recommendations or programmes.

D3.5, conducted by Institut LYFE (LYFE) in partnership with Fundació Alícia (FA) and the University of Milan (UMIL) designed a study, *Sacrilege on a Plate (SoaP)* to investigate how changes to recipes are perceived and which modifications are more likely to challenge their recognisability. D3.5 reports the first phase, “Survey on Typicality,” of a three-step cross-cultural study conducted in seven European countries to identify culturally typical dishes, characterise the relative importance of ingredients within recipes, and establish an empirical framework for investigating ingredient substitution.

Based on the completed phase on European representations of typicality, this deliverable offers a salient framework for addressing current limitations and barriers to navigating recipe flexibility and rigidity in shared representations and perceptions: ***structured flexibility***.

Based on the *SoaP* study and typicality survey data collected, D3.5 suggest that adopting a structured flexibility approach can—depending on a recipe’s dimension (in this case, ingredient substitution)—offer significant insights into how recipe’s flexibility and identity is organised, where limits or “stress points” to modifications may arise, and their implications for recognising culturally meaningful representations of European culinary heritage while better responding to sustainability concerns.

This framework responds to the critical and philosophical approaches to recipe identity and flexibility outlined in D4.1 and D4.2, offers conceptual and methodological tools to bridge WP4 approaches with data collected in WP3, and curates results for further analysis with WP4 and WP5.

Bibliography

- Borghini, Andrea, and Matteo Gandolini. 2020. "Recipes, Their Authors, and Their Names." *HUMANA.MENTE Journal of Philosophical Studies* 13 (8):142–62.
- Borghini, Andrea. 2015. "What Is a Recipe?" *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics* 28 (4): 719–38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10806-015-9556-9>.
- Calvo, Manuel. 1982. "Migration et Alimentation." *Social Science Information* 21 (2): 383–446. <https://doi.org/10.1177/053901882021003003>.
- Douglas, Mary. 1972. "Deciphering a Meal." *Daedalus* 101 (1): 61–81.
- Douglas, Mary. 1979. *Les structures du culinaire*. <https://doi.org/10.3406/comm.1979.1475>.
- Garth, Hanna. 2019. "Alimentary Dignity: Defining a Decent Meal in Post-Soviet Cuban Household Cooking." *The Journal of Latin American and Caribbean Anthropology* 24 (2): 424–42. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jlca.12369>.
- Lévi-Strauss, Claude. 1966. *The Savage Mind*. University of Chicago Press, 1966.
- Matta, Raúl, Charles-Edouard de Suremain, and Chantal Crenn, eds. 2020. *Food Identities at Home and on the Move. Explorations at the Intersection of Food, Belonging and Dwelling*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003085430>.
- Nguyen, Simone P., and Gregory L. Murphy. 2003. "An Apple Is More than Just a Fruit: Cross-classification in Children's Concepts." *Child Development* 74 (6): 1783–806.
- Parasecoli, Fabio. 2022. *Gastronativism: Food, Identity, Politics*. Columbia University Press.
- Schank, Roger C., and Robert P. Abelson. 1977. *Scripts, Plans, Goals and Understanding: An Inquiry into Human Knowledge Structures*. Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Sigrist, Marie, and Maxime Michaud. 2023. "Immigrant Entrepreneurs' Culinary, Symbolic, and Commercial Hybridization of Brazilian Food in France." *Food and Foodways* 31 (4): 251–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07409710.2023.2261723>.
- Sutrop, Urmias. 2001. "List Task and a Cognitive Salience Index." *Field Methods* 13 (3): 263–76. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822X0101300303>.
- Turmo, Isabel González. 2004. "A Methodology for Analysing Recipe Books." *Social Science Information* 43 (4): 753–73. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0539018404047717>.
- Willett, Walter, Johan Rockström, Brent Loken, et al. 2019. "Food in the Anthropocene: The EAT-Lancet Commission on Healthy Diets from Sustainable Food Systems." *Lancet (London, England)* 393 (10170): 447–92. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31788-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31788-4).

Annex I: Survey Description and Questions

The following pages enclose the full description and questions for the **D3.5 Survey on Typicality** (English version) for first phases of the *SoaP* study.

The survey versions were administered across seven European countries through the **LabVanced** platform. Recruitment periods and survey links can be found here:

- **UK** (13/12/2025–20/02/2026):
<https://www.labvanced.com/player.html?id=74368>
- **Ireland** (12/12/2025–19/02/2026):
<https://www.labvanced.com/player.html?id=76276>
- **Italy** (12/12/2025–19/02/2026):
<https://www.labvanced.com/player.html?id=76344>
- **Denmark** (12/12/2025–18/02/2026):
<https://www.labvanced.com/player.html?id=76763>
- **France** (12/12/2025–13/02/2026):
<https://www.labvanced.com/player.html?id=76291>
- **Spain** (12/12/2025–13/02/2026):
<https://www.labvanced.com/player.html?id=76757>
- **Portugal** (12/12/2025–13/02/2026):
<https://www.labvanced.com/player.html?id=76760>

Survey on Typicality

Thank you for your interest in our study!

The goal of this study is to understand how people perceive the typical dishes and ingredients of their country's cuisine. You will be asked to list main-course dishes that you consider typical, indicate how familiar you are with them, and provide the ingredients that you think are essential for each dish.

Important notes:

- This study is **not about your personal food preferences or how often you eat these dishes**; we are interested in what is generally considered “typical” in your country's cuisine.
- The survey takes approximately **10–15 minutes** to complete.
- Your responses are **fully anonymous**. No personally identifying information will be collected or stored.

To participate, you must:

- Be **18 years old or older**.
- Hold **the British citizenship**.
- Have **lived at least 10 years in the United Kingdom**.

By clicking “I agree” below, you confirm that you meet the inclusion criteria, understand that your participation is voluntary, and consent to your anonymized responses being used for research purposes.

"I agree"

"I do not agree"

Typical Main-Course Dishes

Please list **6 main-course dishes** that you perceive as **typical of your country's cuisine**, in the order they come to mind.

Do not include appetizers, starters, cheeses, desserts, or drinks.

Here, "typical" means:

- Conforming to cultural expectations about which dishes belong to the **core repertoire** of the United Kingdom's cuisine.
- It is **not about your personal food preferences** or how often you eat them.

Please write **one dish per field**.

Dish 1

Dish 2

Dish 3

Dish 4

Dish 5

Dish 6

Dish Details

Now, we'd like to know a bit more about the dish you listed. Please answer the following questions for **Dish X: XXX**.

How familiar are you with this dish?

For example, Vanessa reported being not at all familiar with this dish because she has only heard about it but never seen or tried it.

In contrast, Robert reported being extremely familiar with this dish because it is always present at his place.

Not at all familiar - Extremely familiar

Approximately how often have you consumed this dish?

- Never
- Once or twice in my life
- A few times a year
- About once a month
- A few times a month
- About once a week
- More than once a week

In which of the following contexts have you consumed or encountered this dish the most?

- Home meals
- Special occasions (e.g., birthdays, weddings, religious or holiday events)
- Dining out at restaurants
- Media exposure only (e.g., seen on TV, social media, cookbooks) but never tasted

Essential Ingredients

For the **Dish X XXX** you listed earlier, please enter **3 to 5 ingredients** that you consider **essential** to the recipe. Enter them in the order that comes to mind.

Ingredient 1

Ingredient 2

Ingredient 3

Ingredient 4

Ingredient 5

Demographics & Background

Do you hold the British citizenship?

- Yes
- No

What is your age (in years)?

For how many total years have you lived in the United Kingdom?

Which region of the United Kingdom do you identify with or have significant experience in (e.g., where you grew up or have lived)?

What is the size of the municipality (commune/town) where you live?

- Less than 2,000
- 2,000 - 10,000
- 10,000 - 100,000
- More than 100,000
- Capital or major metropolitan area

Being British is an important part of who I am.

Strongly disagree – Strongly agree

My connection to [Regional identity] is an important part of who I am.

Strongly disagree – Strongly agree

What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary
- Other
- Prefer not to say

Currently, you're living:

- Alone
- Alone with children (at least part of the time)
- In shared accommodation
- In an institution
- In a couple (without children)
- In a couple with children (at least part of the time)

If you selected "Alone", "In shared accommodation", or "In an institution", did you used to live in a couple or/and with children?

- Yes
- No

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Less than high school
- High school diploma or equivalent
- Some university / vocational training
- Bachelor's degree (or equivalent)
- Master's degree (or equivalent)
- Doctoral degree

How would you describe your current financial situation?

- Live comfortably
- Meet needs with a little left
- Just meet basic expenses
- Do not meet basic expenses

What is your current professional status?

- Working
- Retired
- Student
- Unemployed
- Permanently disabled
- Other inactive aged less than 65 years

If you selected "Working" or "Retired", in which socio-professional category is your work (or your last work if retired) situated?

- Managers (managerial, self-employed, or employees)
- Professionals (e.g., researchers, engineers, doctors, business and administration professionals, lawyers, artists, teachers, architects)
- Technicians and associated professional employees (e.g., engineering, chemical, computer, and telecommunications technicians; caregivers; jurists; legal and social workers; nurses; medical and pharmaceutical technicians; accountants; human resources professionals; administrative and executive secretaries; religious professionals; journalists; librarians; education support professionals)
- Small entrepreneurs (self-employed, e.g., farmers, service providers, shopkeepers, craft workers)

- Clerks and skilled service employees (e.g., office clerks, secretaries, receptionists, typists, customer service clerks, service desk employees, nursing assistants, care assistants, childcare workers, security guards, police officers, police staff, armed forces employees, soldiers)
- Industrial skilled employees (e.g., machinery mechanics and repairers, electrical and electronic trades workers, carpenters, bricklayers, plumbers, precision workers such as toolmakers and engravers, printing trades workers, and other skilled industrial workers involved in production, maintenance, and technical crafts)
- Less-skilled employees (e.g., personal care workers, cleaners, sales assistants, less-skilled laborers in factories or construction sites, agricultural workers)

How often do you cook dishes at home?

- Never or almost never
- A few times a year
- Monthly
- Weekly
- More than once a week
- Daily

Which of the following best describes your current diet?

- Omnivorous (to eat both animal and plant products)
- Flexitarian (mostly plant-based but occasionally eat meat or fish)
- Pescatarian
- Vegetarian (no meat or fish but may consume dairy or eggs)
- Vegan (no animal products including dairy, eggs, honey)
- Other

Do you have any food allergies or intolerances?

- No
- Yes (please specify)

How familiar are you with the United Kingdom's cuisine?

Not at all familiar – Extremely familiar

How familiar are you with the [Regional identity]'s cuisine?

Not at all familiar – Extremely familiar

How often do you eat dishes from the United Kingdom?

Never – Really frequently

How often do you eat dishes from [Regional identity]?

Never – Really frequently

Annex II: Survey Datasets

The data accompanying this deliverable are provided as two harmonised datasets at complementary levels of analysis. The first dataset is organised at the **dish level**, whereas the second is organised at the **ingredient level**, with each ingredient linked to its corresponding parent dish. Together, these datasets provide the empirical foundation for the analyses reported in D3.5 and support future secondary analyses and cross-country comparisons.

For each dish (and, in the ingredient-level dataset, for the corresponding parent dish), the datasets include the harmonised canonical name, frequency of mention (F), mean recall rank, and Cognitive Salience Index (CSI). They also provide descriptive information on participants' familiarity and experience with each dish, including the distribution of reported consumption frequencies (from never consumed to more than once a week), the primary contexts in which the dish is encountered (home meals, special occasions, restaurant consumption, or media exposure only), and the mean familiarity rating (1–100) with its associated standard deviation.

The ingredient-level dataset additionally reports the same salience indicators (F, mean recall rank, and CSI) for each ingredient within its parent recipe while retaining the descriptive information associated with the corresponding dish. This enables ingredient salience to be interpreted within the broader context of the recipe to which it belongs.

Both datasets are organised by participating country and are also provided for the overall sample and for demographic subgroups (sex, age group, and combined sex × age groups), facilitating comparisons across populations and supporting future analyses of cultural variation in shared culinary representations.

The following stable links bring readers to the digital location to view and download public datasets from the RELISH survey on typicality:

- **Dishes_dataset** (2026): <https://zenodo.org/records/21062051>
- **Ingredients_dataset** (2026): <https://zenodo.org/records/21062261>